

The child process created by On-demand-fork may read unexpected data which does not belong to itself. The program (tlb_vulnerability.c) is used to demonstrate the problem. The program does the following:

- 1) The parent process writes the string "helloworld" on each page.
- 2) The parent process calls fork to create a child process.
- 3) The parent process calls *modify_page_table_without_writing_page()*. This function is used to simulate the behavior of page migration. Some pages are migrated from old page frames to new page frames.
- 4) The parent process calls *touch_pages()*. In this function, the parent process allocates new memory space and writes the string "Parent's private data!" on each page.
- 5) During the time of step 3 and 4, the child process traverses its memory space to read the data of each page. The expected result will be that the child process gets "helloworld". However, the child process gets "Parent's private data!" when it is created by On-demand-fork.

In practice, the child process can access data of any other process (not just the parent process); it depends on which process is using the old page frames (in the sample program, the old page frames are allocated to the parent process coincidentally).